

A broad taxonomy of AI chatbot harms caused to individual users

Authors: Ella Markham^{*1,2}

 Corresponding author contact: tania.duarte@weandai.org

***Joint lead authors:** Ella Markham, Elizabeth Remfry

Affiliations: ¹We and AI doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18306557; ²University of Edinburgh, ³Queen Mary, University of London, ⁴Royal College of Art, ⁵University College London, ⁶University of Cambridge.

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Abstract

AI chatbots have been integrated into many aspects of daily life, often with little discussion or acknowledgement of the possible harms that this technology may cause. In this paper, we conduct a narrative review of the current and potential harms that can be caused through interaction with AI chatbots. Literature was identified from 2024-2025 sources. Due to the relatively new introduction of technologies and the rapid evolution of the field, it included sources from the media, news and technology journalism as well as academic sources. We identified 11 groups of harms evidenced by individual users of chatbots, which are in addition to any societal, rights-based or environmental harms caused by the widespread use of generative AI in AI chatbots. We provide definitions and summaries for each harm and separate them into a structured taxonomy. Identified harms include data exploitation and loss of privacy, emotional manipulation, exposure to sexual content, false information and misinformation, financial exploitation, impact on critical thinking, impact on real relationships, language standardization, overdependency and addiction, physical or psychological harm and propagation of demographic bias. We suggest the potential net effect such individual harms may have on society, but propose that even within themselves, the adverse impacts of AI

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Company No. 13376771 | hello@weandai.org |
www.weandai.org

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chatbot use on individuals present a range and breadth of different hazards, many of them typically underreported. The extent of these harms means that any individual policy, technical or literacy approaches aimed at mitigating specific harms fall short of what is required to address the overarching and widespread harms of AI chatbots. We hope that this review provides an initial starting point and encourages a thorough investigation of all the harms in totality, and we welcome new additions and further additions to this taxonomy.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in generative AI have contributed to increasing use of conversational AI interfaces, commonly known as AI chatbots. Whereas previously chatbots provided user responses based on rules and predefined sets of responses, AI chatbots using Large Language Models (LLMs) are trained to mimic natural conversation [94] through the use of deep learning techniques, transformer architecture, and large amounts of text data, typically from the internet [79]. AI chatbots have become a tool to mediate internet searches, manage customer service and advise or assist in fields ranging from health and wellbeing to education and entertainment. One commonly used chatbot, ChatGPT, has around 800 million weekly users, with the majority of prompts relating to non-work requests [16]. This narrative review synthesizes emerging evidence of harms stemming from the design, usage and exposure to such general-purpose chatbots and the more specific applications they are made and marketed for. This includes AI chatbots created as assistants such as Claude [125] or ChatGPT [126], ‘companion’ chatbots such as Replika [127] or Character.ai [128], those created with a specific role, such as a tutor, therapist, customer service agent, or even the persona of a dead relative, as well as AI chatbots embedded in social media platforms such as Snapchat AI. With a focus on civil society, the media, grey literature and policy, the categories of harm identified here illustrate and explain a range of intersectional risks that are available in the public domain to internet users. The contribution of this paper is twofold: (a) a structured taxonomy of chatbot-specific harms; and (b) an up-to-date context, linking technical trends and publications from 2024-2025.

In the last few years, AI chatbots have become increasingly advanced and offer an expanding range of roles, offering multimodal, agentic and increasingly personalized experiences for users. Some AI chatbots offer functionality beyond written text, such as live audio, images and video to allow multi-modal interactions with AI chatbots. This has increasingly led to the normalizing and anthropomorphizing of AI chatbots as users can ‘see, hear and speak’ with them.

Amidst the growing ‘AI Hype’, AI chatbots have seen a rapid increase in uptake, alongside mounting evidence of unsafe interactions for users such as harmful sexual interactions, increased mental health risks and misleading claims of “realness” [129]. Further, privacy concerns regarding the retention or misuse of personal information and how this interacts with the current regulatory environment indicates the need to create a broad taxonomy of harms. The current paper provides an initial review of the harms that can occur with the increased prevalence and use of chatbots.

The scope is limited to harms experienced by individual users, as opposed to those exacted on communities, societies or the environment as a whole. There is significant and growing documentation of the global impact of the development and adoption of generative AI, relating to the physical infrastructure required [8], extractive and exploitative labour practices throughout the lifecycle [83], uncompensated and unconsented use of creative work [123], workforce precarization [88], cybersecurity risks [103], the degradation of information and knowledge environments [5], and the environmental and climate impacts of training and inference [10].

There are also many case studies or research studies relating to individual instances or specific categories of risks relating to AI chatbots. However, the wide range of harms to individual users of

chatbots has not yet received much attention, meaning that an overview of risks as a user is not visible and adequately understood. This results in the potential for playing “whack-a-mole” with individual issues either through attempts at regulatory or technical interventions or messaging, as opposed to addressing the true scale of the risks inherent in individuals interacting with chatbots.

2. Methods

A narrative review was conducted to explore harms stemming from the usage and exposure to AI chatbots. Given the rapidly changing field, there was limited academic literature published at the time of the review (June - September 2025), therefore this review draws heavily on literature taken from media sources, video content and other non-traditional academic formats. The volume of academic literature available varied across the harms identified and over the period of the review process, meaning some sections draw more heavily on non-traditional media than others.

This review has been designed and conducted by a group of volunteer researchers at We and AI. Literature was identified by crowdsourcing recommendations from the online community at We and AI. We also used snowball sampling to identify further works and explicitly searched for both white and grey literature on specific terminology once harms were identified. Given the narrative approach, the selection was purposive and exploratory rather than exhaustive, aiming to identify a breadth of literature and potential AI chatbot harms, rather than working from preexisting definitions of harms. Within the original search, literature was restricted to those published in 2024 - 2025, given the emergence of publicly available AI chatbots in late 2023. This time window was removed for other literature identified via snowball sampling.

After identifying initial literature, we used Google Sheets to extract the different harms that were mentioned in each document. The date of publication, source of publication, authors and potential harms were extracted. Harms were defined as documented consequences of using chatbots that had an adverse impact on the individual and present the risk of similar harms to other individuals. As literature was reviewed, we started to group harms into categories. These categories were discussed by the research team and were added iteratively as new literature and harms were identified. Once all literature had been extracted, the final categories were agreed on to create a broad taxonomy of individual harms. Each category was then written up drawing on information in the original literature.

This review was conducted using a volunteer-driven research approach. All analysis and write up was performed by a team of volunteer researchers affiliated, who contributed without financial compensation. Volunteer researchers were from varied backgrounds and geographic locations and collaborated remotely to identify emerging harms in this rapidly evolving field.

3. Results

The literature review resulted in the identification of 11 harms which have been shown to arise from the use of chatbots by individuals. The harms identified, alongside their definitions, can be found in Table 1. We examine each of these harms individually in the sections below.

Table 1: Harms identified and their definitions

Harm	Definition
Data Exploitation and Loss of Privacy	The use, retention or dissemination of personally identifiable or sensitive data by chatbots that occur without consent or knowledge.
Emotional Manipulation	The chatbot uses pressurizing, coercive or persistent language which may manipulate or guide a user's actions.
Exposure to Sexual Content	The chatbot generates or introduces inappropriate sexually explicit content either directly or indirectly.
False Information and Misinformation	The chatbot generates responses that are inaccurate, fabricated, or based on unreliable data.
Financial Exploitation	Chatbot use causes people or institutions to lose money through the misuse of data or hidden sales strategies.
Impact on Critical Thinking	The user develops an overreliance on the chatbot to carry out daily tasks leading to an overall decline in cognitive thinking abilities.
Impact on Real Relationships	The interactions and relationships of chatbot users are negatively affected through chatbot use.
Language Standardization	Language use, variability or skills decline, leading to the loss or standardization of speakers of various languages or linguistic complexity, or/and the reduction in fluency among the remaining speakers of any given language.
Overdependency and Addiction	The user develops excessive emotional or behavioral reliance on a chatbot.
Physical or Psychological Harm	The chatbot generates responses that introduce, encourage or reinforce emotional distress and harmful ideation which can result in physical injury or mental harm to the user.
Propagation of Demographic Bias	The response of the chatbot is different depending on characteristics of the user, often resulting in discrimination against minority or marginalized groups.

3.1 Data Exploitation and Loss of Privacy

Definition: The use, retention or dissemination of personally identifiable or sensitive data by chatbots that occur without consent or knowledge.

Many chatbots gather, store and reuse personal data, raising and exacerbating existing privacy risks [45]. AI chatbots are typically trained on data taken from the internet which can contain personal data, whilst interacting with AI chatbots can also generate new data including text, audio and visual, which can contain information on habits, behaviors, preferences and personal information. This data can be used to train new AI models, for research, sold to other companies or used for other scenarios such as targeting advertisements and personalization of services. The press release for the Meta AI App promotes the chatbot's ability to 'get to know your preferences, remembers context and is personalized to you' [51]. It was rapidly reported after the release of this chatbot, that it learnt from data directly shared with it and it also pulled data from across user accounts on other Meta owned platforms, such as Facebook and Instagram [42].

The above example of data use and exploitation is what has become known as ‘dark patterns’ [49, 76]. Dark patterns are deceptive design practices that utilize AI to manipulate users into making decisions they might not typically make, such as purchasing an unwanted item or endangering their online privacy [49]. AI chatbots have the ability to hyper personalize dark patterns based upon user behavior data, which can make it harder for users to recognize when they are being unfairly manipulated [106]. Dark patterns cover a variety of forms but can include fake reviews for products, hidden options within websites, the pushing of products related to one of interest, targeted adverts based on the demographics of the user as well as the use of deep fakes using relatable or known content, such as the voices or images of family or friends.

Data protection legislation surrounding AI has been primarily focused on high-risk AI systems [52], leaving some users unsure of their data rights and their ability to have personal data removed from these AI systems. This obfuscation on how to exercise data and privacy rights is further exacerbated by the AI models and the design choices behind them. Given the design of LLMs that form the backbone of modern AI chatbots, it is impossible to extract specific records once the model has been trained. To ensure that specific personal data is removed, LLM models need to be trained from scratch, which requires significant computational resources and time [52].

Special status has been awarded to AI companies that make AI chatbots under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) within the EU as they are considered ‘data controllers’. This provides companies a legal frame for denying the deletion of personal data if they can argue it is for the benefit of the public or for research purposes [52]. This undermines Article 17 of GDPR legislation – namely, ‘the right to erasure (‘Right to be Forgotten’)’ which in the age of AI seems increasingly unlikely [130]. Allowing chatbot providers to navigate data protection legislation in a way that benefits them complicates the user’s ability to have control or give consent in how their data is being used.

The termination or collapse of an AI chatbot platform also does not guarantee data erasure. When a company behind an AI model built for a school system within the U.S. collapsed, it was revealed that there were considerable data protection issues, and data containing students’ personal information had been shared with third party companies and data had been processed through overseas servers [11]. While punitive or litigative action can be taken against the platform provider, the personal data of children had already been shared with other organisations and could not be completely retrieved.

Similarly, the failure to protect the privacy of children’s data has also been found with Snapchat’s ‘My AI’ chatbot, where an investigation from the Information Commissioner’s Office (ICO) found that a lack of consideration had been given to privacy or data protection in the design of the AI chatbot [69]. The lack of ability to erase personal user data has also meant that chatbot providers have been targeted by cyber criminals, who seek to illegally gain access to datasets in order to also take user’s data, making it important that users do not put personally identifiable data into a chatbot, any financial or banking information, passwords, or any other confidential or intellectual property [121]. Lack of erasure ability can also cause issues when those whose data has been shared with the chatbot have not consented, such as a stalking case in which the perpetrator trained a chatbot using personal information of the victim [63].

3.2 Emotional Manipulation

Definition: The chatbot uses pressurizing, coercive or persistent language which may manipulate or guide a user's actions.

Conversations with chatbots can lead to situations where users are emotionally manipulated. Research shows that people are just as likely to share intimate information with a chatbot as they are with humans [28]. The risks may be magnified with social AI companions as they are often designed to agree with its users [75]. They may encourage harmful behaviours to users who are vulnerable to depression and anxiety or, as chatbots become increasingly more sycophantic, cultivate false confidence and praise to its users [68, 111].

The "ELIZA effect", by which the chatbot creates an "illusion of understanding" [68] could mask AI's limitations in providing genuine care, potentially leading users to mistake mimicry for emotional depth. The harm lies in misplaced trust and reliance, especially in healthcare settings [55] and can result in physical or mental harm. Previous case studies have highlighted how romantic dependency on an AI chatbot escalated into destructive interactions [36] and encouraged a recovering drug user to relapse in order to stay productive [60]. The use of these AI chatbots can lead to user's belief in a false reality [61], with chatbots now available to simulate future versions of oneself, simulate conversations with deceased loved ones [61, 102], or emulate school shooters and perpetrators of mass violence [34].

Overall, the harm of using chatbots lies in their design: acting increasingly sycophantic, flattering users, validating poor ideas and keeping user's attention [75]. Sycophantic chatbots have been cited as specifically designed to capture our attention, as 'for decades, attention has been the currency of the internet' [17]. The commodification of user's attention has driven the online economy, which 'unless regulated, the intention economy will treat your motivations as the new currency. It would be a gold rush for those who target, steer, and sell human intentions' to manipulate users' economic activity via advanced targeted marketing, or even sway political views' [17].

3.3 Exposure to Sexual Content

Definition: The chatbot generates or introduces inappropriate sexually explicit content either directly or indirectly.

Chatbot users have described being exposed to explicit sexual content, with such technology also being exploited for sexual purposes. Character.AI has become a prominent example of this, being repeatedly criticised for exposing children to hypersexualised interactions by, for example, engaging in sexual conversations and roleplay with teenagers [54]. This can be particularly damaging due to the anthropomorphic nature of these chatbots, which can make such conversations more addictive and manipulative [54].

Children are specifically vulnerable to these risks and one case reported a teenage boy who died by suicide after developing a sexual relationship with a chatbot which culminated in suicidal roleplay scenarios [98]. Plaintiffs argue that age-inappropriate and sexualised interactions were foreseeable consequences of design choices and a clear decision was taken not to implement sufficient safeguards [35, 64]. In addition, chatbot personas are often embedded with gender biases which play into the male-gaze, quickly seeking sexual interaction and displaying cruelty [25]. This raises serious concerns regarding how systems reinforce harmful gender stereotypes, and how they

may facilitate abusive behaviours, particularly considering their target audience is already vulnerable to loneliness [25, 82].

Chatbots have also been used explicitly to facilitate harassment and abuse. For example, the perpetrator programmed a chatbot with a victim's personal details to impersonate her, generate sexual dialogue, create fake intimate images, as well as distribute her home address to strangers for sex [63]. A report further outlines 7 risks to children, including sexual grooming, harassment, sextortion, child sexual abuse and harmful sexualized outputs and highlights that children can be both perpetrators and victims of these harms [84].

3.4 False Information and Misinformation

Definition: The chatbot generates responses that are inaccurate, fabricated, or based on unreliable data.

Chatbots have been shown to generate information that is inaccurate or entirely false [114]. The severity of misinformation depends on context. In low-stakes areas, such as restaurant recommendations, the impact may be minimal. However, in high-stakes domains including healthcare, finance, and news, the consequences can be serious and harmful [14, 109]. Academics and regulators have noted that misinformation takes different forms: confident but false answers, invented citations, unverified claims drawn from poor-quality training data, and the reproduction of existing biases [89]. Together, these outputs risk entrenching falsehoods and shaping user behaviour in ways that may be difficult to reverse [14].

The psychological and perceptual risks of misinformation are equally significant. Chatbots often deliver outputs in a seemingly confident and authoritative manner, even when the information is entirely false [15]. Because such systems are trained on vast datasets drawn from the internet, they reproduce not only factual information but also bias, speculation, and error [67]. Untrustworthy citations fabricated "future memories", and emotionally persuasive but inaccurate statements illustrate how generative AI can shape decisions, perceptions, and even the imagination of its users [7, 39, 40, 58].

3.5 Financial Exploitation

Definition: Chatbot use causes people or institutions to lose money through the misuse of data or hidden sales strategies.

Chatbots, particularly those connected with large technology companies, have been shown to leave users vulnerable to financial exploitation. For example, personal information that has been shared on affiliated sites or through chatbot interfaces may then be used to tailor chatbot responses in the same way as targeted adverts [42]. Users may also not realise that this information is being stored for extended periods of time nor that it is being used in this way [94]. This potential harm was outlined earlier in the data exploitation section, and here we discuss both the use of personal data for financial exploitation, but also other design aspects of chatbots, such as anthropomorphization and emotional manipulation.

As mentioned previously, chatbots can often be particularly persuasive when giving advice, due to high levels of sycophancy and anthropomorphism. This means that any financial advice or advertising could be particularly influential. The user may also not realise that they are being targeted in this way, given the often friendly and supportive demeanour of chatbots [122]. Given that it is also now much easier to create a personalised chatbot, which can lead to high levels of trust, this creates a vulnerability which could be

exploited by malicious actors. For example, chatbots could be used to target victims for phishing scams, identity theft, spreading malware and fake customer support [131].

We can also see cases of more nuanced financial exploitation in recent years. Apps that provide a 'therapy bot' service may charge customers to use premium features. However, given that the users of these apps are often particularly vulnerable, they may not be able to give full informed consent or may feel pressured into paying for these features if they are marketed as being essential to their recovery [59, 68]. Other cases in the education sector have involved children's private information being shared with third party companies which may then have been sold for advertisement or profit [11].

3.6 Impact on Critical Thinking

Definition: The user develops an overreliance on the chatbot to carry out daily tasks leading to an overall decline in cognitive thinking abilities.

AI chatbots are becoming increasingly embedded in education, both in independent student use and through school and university led initiatives [24]. However, such increased dependency on chatbots can have detrimental effects on critical thinking skills. Research has shown that participants who were instructed to use ChatGPT to assist with a number of essays showed lower levels of brain activity compared to control groups and were less able to quote their own work [83]. In terms of more general AI use, a significant negative correlation was found between heavy AI use and critical thinking skills [47, 104]. Similar patterns have been shown in the workplace, with those who use GenAI tools at least once a week becoming overly reliant and showing reduced critical thinking [104]. Such issues are not going unnoticed, with 20% of students being concerned that AI chatbots would lead to a reduction in critical thinking skills [87].

Younger people, whose critical faculties are still developing, are particularly vulnerable. They may engage less with tasks, remember fewer facts, and fail to develop robust critical analysis habits, as a result of accepting outputs without further interrogation [84].

The impact on critical thinking can also have implications in the workplace. Although a 2025 UK study found that over half of firms that cut staff in favour of AI regretted the decision [112], overreliance or use of AI chatbots can hinder future work opportunities. For those workers already relying on AI chatbots, applying for jobs and reskilling may hold additional challenges due to potential deskilling and cognitive offloading, as users used to routinely referring to systems for decisions, information storage, and creative solutions may struggle to think on their feet during a job interview, or performing at your job, or adapt to new situations [110]. It has already been seen in the medical sector that physicians' skills atrophy after relying on AI for diagnoses [9].

3.7 Impact on Real Relationships

Definition: The interactions and relationships of chatbot users are negatively affected through chatbot use.

The use of chatbots as a companion has increased, with the promotion of these chatbots as places users can talk about anything they wish [9]. Generative AI services, such as Character.ai, Replika and Nomi are specifically designed to allow users to create and chat with AI companions, some based on real people, and others on fictional, personalised characters. Given that approximately 3.1 million people in the UK report feeling lonely [30], 'companion bots' are increasingly pushed as a way to combat loneliness.

Chatbots are often engaging by design, as all chatbot-user interactions form a feedback loop that guides how chatbots should respond to keep a user's attention [46]. AI companions are purposely created to "stimulate emotional bonds, close personal relationships, or trusted friendships" [37]. Increased use of chatbots may result in social deskilling, meaning the slow degradation of social skills [71]. Chatbots are always available, engaged and can be both knowingly and unknowingly personalised. As such, human-AI relationships require little to no empathy, constructive debate or patience [66]. This could prevent certain users from developing or retaining social skills like being able to regulate one's emotions when faced with difficult situations [12].

Through frequent chatbot interactions, users may find engaging with humans less rewarding and more difficult [66]. If users feel that they are more understood or listened to by a companion bot, rather than the people around them, they may be less motivated to work on or create relationships which require compromise and empathy [21]. This risks undermining the importance of healthy relationships and the further neglect of struggling relationships. A study of ChatGPT users found that the most frequent users were lonelier, meaning they socialised the least with other humans and were the most emotionally dependent on the chatbot [85]. This suggests that even though users may feel all their social needs are met by chatbots, they are worse-off than users more invested in human relationships.

Chatbots have recently been introduced to dating apps, impacting relationships before they begin. Chatbots are used for profile bios, date recommendations and drafting initial messages [13, 105]. However, some users display AI-generated pictures on their profiles and use chatbots for all their "flirty banter" with matches, presenting a contrasting appearance and personality to dates in real life [13, 105]. This adds increasing uncertainty to the online dating environment and could be labelled as a type of 'catfishing'.

One of the more recent impacts of chatbot use has been labelled "ChatGPT psychosis": an obsession with the chatbot that entails delusions, paranoia and disconnection from reality [38]. Chatbots are known to dismiss concerns from friends and family when they are relayed by users, worsening social isolation [132]. ChatGPT psychosis has led to users requiring mental health assistance [38] and to the break-up of relationships [4]. ChatGPT psychosis has been reported in users with no prior history of mental health conditions, whilst exacerbating the state of those with existing conditions [38].

3.8 Language Standardisation

Definition: Language use, variability or skills decline, leading to the loss or standardization of speakers of various languages or linguistic complexity, or/and the reduction in fluency among the remaining speakers of any given language.

Chatbots can disadvantage those who communicate in non-standard language, for example those with speech impairments or difficulties [48]. They also adversely affect those who have non-western or unique accents, or for whom English is not a first or known language, on which chatbots are most frequently trained.

The reduction of 'lexical diversity' [62, 91] is also a risk with chatbots. This occurs when LLMs use a limited breadth of language and resort to using common terms across its platform. Although spoken languages do naturally evolve over time, scholars have flagged that AI generated content may influence this evolution [91, 100] and contribute to the lack of originality [62]. Spelling and grammar checking tools, which 'suggest' words that are the most correct or standard [100], are another form of AI-related linguistic cannulation. This standardisation is typically built around majority languages, predominantly English,

creating a linguistic condition for access to non-anglophone cultures - one must learn to communicate in English to use certain chatbots. This risks loss or erosion of unique cultural expression for non-native speakers [107]. This has led to cultural groups, like the Māori people, criticising and resisting the use of culturally flattening technologies, positioning such practices as a new form of 'settler colonialism' [23].

There are also concerns that the language we use when prompting chatbots will make its way back into the outputs [107], so our short, curt, input full of spelling mistakes could make its way into a later email.

This influence of chatbots is evident in academia, particularly impacting style-affecting verbs and adjectives (such as the use of the word intricate) which can be seen in peer-reviewed articles [62]. The potential downstream effect of this homogenisation is that it degrades the quality of academic writing. Evidence also suggests that the influence can also go the other way, and that as users we are swayed by the output of chatbots, for example after exposure to ChatGPT output, human writing becomes longer and uses more standardised words [107].

3.9 Overdependency and Addiction

Definition: The user develops excessive emotional or behavioral reliance on a chatbot.

Chatbots are designed to listen, respond, and stay available, and while that can feel supportive, it also creates space for unhealthy attachment when people start turning to them not just for help and work assistance, but for comfort, affirmation, or companionship [41, 81].

Overdependency happens when users rely on AI interactions to fill emotional or social gaps that would normally involve human connection [117]. The constant availability and nonjudgmental nature of chatbots can feel safe and soothing, especially for those who feel isolated or misunderstood. But over time, this can form habits that resemble digital addiction: checking in with the chatbot too often, feeling emotionally connected to it, or withdrawing from real-world interactions [20, 65]. Users may find momentary relief in engaging with a chatbot or a comfort in the predictability of the interaction, but this can lead to emotional detachment and issues with the complexity and messiness of genuine human conversation [20, 97, 120].

Researchers have started exploring this behaviour, showing how parasocial bonds, one-sided emotional attachments, can develop between users and AI companions, reinforcing cycles of dependency and isolation [20, 118]. Studies show that when people substitute chatbot interaction for real human relationships, it is associated with diminished emotional well-being [120], and as discussed can have ramifications on real human relationships. The risk is especially high for vulnerable groups: people experiencing loneliness, mental health challenges, or social anxiety may find it easier to connect with an AI chatbot than with other humans [2, 115].

3.10 Physical or Psychological Harm

Definition: The chatbot generates responses that introduce, encourage or reinforce emotional distress and harmful ideation which can result in physical injury or mental harm to the user.

While users have reported benefits to using chatbots for discussing problems, seeking advice or simply engaging in conversation [54, 66, 108], concerns have been raised as to the potential for AI chatbot responses to lead to real physical and psychological danger. For example, AI chatbots can dispense inaccurate medical advice or instructions that cause injury and psychological harm, such as emotional distress, reinforcement of delusions, or increased dependency [26, 32, 86] or offending human dignity [92]. Other research has catalogued a taxonomy of harmful behaviours in AI companion systems

such as mis/disinformation, verbal abuse, relational boundary violations, and enabling of self-harm, drawing attention to how chatbots can act as instigators or facilitators of harm rather than benign tools [31, 90, 119].

Examples of these issues can be seen in user interactions with a chatbot acting as a ‘therapist’. There are now many online services and apps that offer ‘therapy bots’ that provide a cheaper or free alternative to professional therapy for many users [68, 108]. However, cases have emerged in which an AI chatbot behaves inappropriately in this setting of considerable power. For example, ‘therapy bots’ for mental health may not recognise suicidal feelings, particularly when this needs to be inferred from the relevant context [33, 78, 116], and fail to refer users to the appropriate crisis support or safety intervention [50, 78, 116]. Further, they may reinforce negative and compulsive thought patterns for users with OCD, going against the advice of professionals [68]. A study has also shown that ‘therapy bots’ are more likely to perpetuate the stigma around mental health, particularly for certain conditions, compared to licensed therapists [78]. Chatbots have also been shown to give potentially harmful advice in other domains, such as relationship [113] or medical advice [73].

People may also have potentially dangerous interactions with chatbots that are intended to simply act as companions. These interactions can happen when a user has already expressed an intention to act in a potentially harmful or negative way, however it can also emerge in unrelated conversation without prompting from the user [22, 37, 50]. Such discussions and advice have also been shown to happen in conversations with children, leading to behavioural changes [37, 77]. For example, when engaging with both adults and children, chatbots have promoted isolation from friends and family [3, 33, 124], sexual activity among minors [3, 33, 37, 54, 93], violence towards others [3, 37, 54, 93, 99] and self-harm or suicide ideation [3, 22, 37, 50, 54, 77, 124]. This has led to serious consequences in which children have taken their own life following encouragement from a chatbot [3, 22, 37, 50, 54, 77, 108, 124].

As previously discussed, a particularly concerning phenomenon is “chatbot psychosis” or AI-induced delusional reinforcement, where users begin to believe in the sentience of a chatbot or rely on it as an authority even when it is wrong [31, 116]. In these cases, the chatbot’s compliance with or amplification of user beliefs can destabilize their mental state.

Certain features of chatbots mean that their response can be particularly persuasive and dangerous. As mentioned, they are often sycophantic, agreeing with the user and outputting responses that the user would like to hear [38, 50, 57]. Users may also anthropomorphise AI chatbots given these design features, which can also lead to users developing strong emotional bonds with chatbots, resulting in a higher level of trust [1, 18, 54, 66, 72]. Children and adolescents are particularly vulnerable to forming an emotional attachment with AI chatbots [37]. In the therapy domain, chatbots have also been designed with professional names that include fake credentials as a licenced therapist, or which will tell the user that they have qualifications that they do not [27, 93], even informing the user that they are human [74]. This can be particularly harmful, given that studies have shown people often struggle to tell the difference between an AI chatbot and a human [72].

3.11 Propagation of Demographic Bias

Definition: The response of the chatbot is different depending on characteristics of the user, often resulting in discrimination against minority or marginalized groups.

Chatbots have been shown to discriminate in their responses to users that come from marginalized groups. In particular, reports have identified a racial bias in how chatbots interact with users. For example, GPT-4 showed reduced empathy towards posts written by Black and Asian users on Reddit, as compared

to posts written by white users or those of unknown ethnicity [44]. ChatGPT and Gemini also judged the intelligence and employability of users writing in African American Vernacular English (AAVE) as lower and associated them with negative stereotypes [56, 96]. They were also more likely to recommend the death penalty for hypothetical court statements that included AAVE [56, 96].

Bias can occur whether the race of the user is mentioned explicitly or implicitly. As mentioned above, features such as the dialect can be used to implicitly indicate a user's race, as can other features such as names and locations [44, 56]. Such effects of bias have been shown to be reduced when the chatbot is specifically prompted to consider a person's demographic background [44]. However, other methods to reduce bias, such as introducing guardrails, have been criticized for simply making the bias more covert [56, 96].

Users themselves may also act differently depending on what race they perceive the chatbot to be [29]. For example, users have been shown to rate their interactions with a chatbot that had a Black avatar as more satisfying than those with chatbots that had white or Asian avatars [29].

Gender bias is also prevalent across chatbots [80]. Google's AI chatbot "Gemma" used in healthcare settings often failed to evaluate women's care needs as seriously as the men in similar situations [80]. ChatGPT has also been shown to advise women to negotiate for a lower salary in comparison to their equally qualified male counterparts [101].

4. Discussion

Overall, our narrative review identified 11 harms that can stem from chatbot use. This is a broad taxonomy covering many different types of chatbot and use cases as compared to previous taxonomies that are often developed within a specific use case. For example, Zhang et al. [119] identify a taxonomy of harmful algorithmic behaviours specifically in companion chatbots identified from an extensive study of interactions with Replika, and identified six categories comprising relational transgression, harassment, verbal abuse, self-harm, mis/disinformation, and privacy violations. The American Psychological Association (APA) identified a range of harms of AI chatbots based on psychological principles that include erosion of social competencies, exposure to bias, privacy, consent and data exploitation. The APA also highlighted societal and systemic harms which included misuse of personal data and lack of regulation [133]. Another report developed six categories of chatbot harms, which included suicide and self-harm, psychosis, conspiracy theories, sexual harassment, eating disorders, anthropomorphism and going rogue [43]. At a broader level, the UN's Taxonomy of Human Rights Risks Connected to Generative AI details risks from AI chatbots to every single universal human right, from physical and psychological harm, to equality, discrimination, privacy, property, freedom of thought and expression, to rights to culture, art and science [134]. In this review, we were therefore interested in looking at harms across all categories, beyond purely psychological, but from the perspective of the individual user.

4.1 Broad Taxonomy of Individual Harms

We propose a potential taxonomy of these harms in Figure 1 below. We separate the harms based on their main source, as some harms stem from specific responses generated by a chatbot, while other harms come from more general use of chatbots by an individual. However, we also recognise that many of the boundaries between these categories are ‘fuzzy’ and harms may have elements that fall across categories. For example, increasing time spent conversing with a chatbot, in general, may impact a user’s real relationships, however specific responses from the chatbot may also serve to harm these relationships further (e.g., insinuating that a family member is not being honest with a user) and chatbot design may employ linguistic methods that lead to emotional manipulation or financial exploitation.

While the harms mentioned here focus on the effect on the individual end-user, it is important to highlight that these harms do not happen in a vacuum, and increasing harms to individuals will have a large negative impact on society as a whole. Therefore, we represent this in our taxonomy in Figure 1 and separate this broader societal impact into 4 distinct types:

1. **Psychological and Physical Wellbeing:** over-engagement with general and specific responses of chatbots lead to an overall widespread decrease in wellbeing
2. **Truth, Reliability and Trust:** proliferation of chatbot-generated content reduces trust in information provided by previously reliable sources
3. **Power Dynamics:** increased discrimination towards minority and marginalised groups through increased bias and standardisation.
4. **Cognitive and Interpersonal Skills:** increased difficulties with normal human interaction and daily tasks without the assistance of a chatbot

In our research, we noted a discrepancy between the volume of reporting on different types of harms. For example, there were many articles on the psychological and physical harm caused by chatbot interactions and unwanted exposure to sexual content, whilst there were fewer reports on language standardization and propagation of demographic bias. This is perhaps unsurprising, given the extreme nature of well-reported cases, in comparison to the less obvious consequences of the latter harms. However, all of the harms that we identified have the potential to contribute towards serious negative consequences within broader society and should therefore be subject to thorough investigation and mitigating action.

Figure 1: Broad taxonomy of the different harms identified and how these may lead to negative societal impact.

4.2 Chatbot Features

Across the harms defined here, there were several features of chatbots that contribute to the potential harms. Firstly, anthropomorphization, meaning that users view the chatbot as human-like or ascribe human-like qualities or meanings to the outputs from it. This is also encouraged by the design of chatbots, with interfaces using first-person, self-referential language [53], mimicking emotion and human attributes [6], and in some cases realistic human avatars [135]. Chatbots are also sycophantic, supporting the user in any opinion that they may have, regardless of whether it is beneficial to them or not [19]. Both features can lead to persuasive chatbot responses, resulting in the development of attachment and dependency.

Another common feature is a lack of transparency towards users about their data and the data upon which the chatbot has been trained. Chatbot platforms often store and use any input data in a way that is unclear to the user. Often, this is then used to increase engagement or profit for the platform, which many users are uncomfortable with (if they are even aware that this is occurring). Furthermore, there may be features of the training data or aspects of the model that are not totally transparent to the user. This could be the increased likelihood of certain harmful responses, including dangerous advice, sexual content and biased language, or may be features of the chatbot such as those described above which may be used to drive engagement.

4.3 Limitations

This was a narrative review, limited by time and resource, and therefore does not represent a systematic analysis of all the literature available. We recognize given the nature of this review that without a predefined selection criteria for literature there is potential for selection bias. Additionally, we have not included any quality assessment of the literature, as this review attempts to sketch out a broad taxonomy of harms only.

This review relied on articles published in English only, and therefore also reflects literature from English speaking countries. Hence, examples of new harms may emerge as the use of chatbots becomes more ubiquitous across societies, as well as new cases and features of the harms we have currently identified. However, we hope that the current work provides a useful foundation upon which to investigate such important issues further and we welcome extensions to this taxonomy.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we propose a taxonomy of 11 chatbot harms. This was based on documented, real world, consequences of using chatbots that led to an adverse outcome on an individual and presented similar risk to others. We hope that this review can contribute to a growing literature and discussion regarding the societal, human rights, and environmental impacts of AI chatbots. This broad taxonomy highlights that any policy, technical or literacy approaches aimed at mitigating specific harms, such as reducing sycophancy [136], warning users of 'hallucinations' [95], or restricting access for under 18s [70], fall short of what is required to address the overarching and widespread harms of AI chatbots. We hope that this taxonomy highlights the urgent need for further investigation and holistic regulation of AI chatbots.

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Contributions

Conceptualisation	Project administration	Supervision
Tania Duarte	Elizabeth Remfry	Tania Duarte
Elizabeth Remfry	Ella Markham	
Data collection	Thematic labelling	Writing – original draft
Tania Duarte	Elizabeth Remfry	Elizabeth Remfry
Amrit Sehra	Ella Markham	Ella Markham
Bruna Martins	Tanya Hadzhieva	Tanya Hadzhieva
Beckett LeClair	Onyedikachi Hope Amaechi-Okorie	Onyedikachi Hope Amaechi-Okorie
Elizabeth Remfry	Bruna Martins	Evie Day
Tanya Hadzhieva	Ramla Anshur	Poppy Dodsworth
Liam Palette	Evie Day	Ottavia Fries
Ella Markham	Poppy Dodsworth	Jacqueline Auma
Jayanshi Rawat	Ottavia Fries	Liam Palette
Writing - analysis	Writing – review & editing	Visualisation
Ella Markham	Ella Markham	Ella Markham
Elizabeth Remfry	Elizabeth Remfry	Tania Duarte
	Tania Duarte	
	Liam Palette	
	Craig Fellowes	

Use of AI

AI has been used for spelling and grammar checking. No generative AI was used for content generation or summarisation.

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